

Studies in Metal-Diethyldithiocarbamates

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Spectrophotometric methods have been employed to study the composition as well as the stability constants of metal chelates¹. Janssen² determined the stability constants of copper complexes of several dialkyldithiocarbamic acids spectrophotometrically, using a competition method involving 8-hydroxyquinoline or 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with the dithiocarbamate. In the present investigation, the composition of metal-diethyldithiocarbamates of copper, nickel, and uranyl ions have been studied and it has been concluded that the formulae of the complexes are $\text{Cu}(\text{DDTC})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{DDTC})_2$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{DDTC})_3$; DDTC represents the diethyldithiocarbamate ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorbance spectra of the mixtures containing the cation and sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDTC) in different proportions, at various wavelengths are measured and the wavelength at which maximum absorption occurs is determined. In all cases, the absorption spectra of solutions containing metal ion and reagent in different proportions showed peak at the same wavelength (only one complex is formed in each case under the experimental conditions). The Beckman spectrophotometer (DU model no. 2400; serial no. 148458) was employed to study the absorbance. The cuvettes used were standardized by taking one of them as standard and the necessary corrections were made. As the copper and nickel complexes are insoluble in water, they were studied in 80% ethyl alcohol and 75% dioxan respectively. Uranyl complex was found soluble in water in the range of the concentrations studied. Initially, the absorbance of the complex is studied at different wavelengths. The result of the copper complex (1 ml. of 1 mM CuSO_4 + 3 ml. of 10 mM NaDDTC + 0.2 ml of N HCl + 20 ml. of ethyl alcohol + 1 ml. of water) is depicted graphically in fig. 1. From the graph it was found that the maximum absorbance in case of copper complex occurs at 430 m μ wavelength. Similarly, it was found that the maximum absorbance for nickel as well as uranyl complexes occurred at 380 m μ . wavelength. To apply the slope ratio method of Harvey and Manning³, two sets of solutions were prepared. One of them contained the excess of cation and the other the excess of the chelating agent.

1. Rossotti and Rossotti, "The Determination of Stability Constants," 1st edition, 1961, McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., N. Y.
2. Janssen, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1956, **75**, 1411; *ibid.*, 1957, **76**, 827.
3. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

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The following systems were studied by slope ratio method of Harvey and Manning:

$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ 0.005M + NaDDTC 0.05M $\leftarrow$: 75% dioxan $\text{UO}_2(\text{Ac})_2$ 0.001M + NaDDTC 0.01M $\leftarrow$: Water
 $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ 0.05M + NaDDTC 0.0005M $\leftarrow$: 75% dioxan $\text{UO}_2(\text{Ac})_2$ 0.01M + NaDDTC 0.001M $\leftarrow$: Water

To apply Job's method⁴ of continuous variation, varying ml. of the cation solution was taken; to it the required ml. of NaDDTC was added, so that the final concentrations of both the species together remained constant. For example, in fig. 3(b), varying ml. of copper

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

sulphate (0.001M) was taken and required ml. of NaDDTC (0.001M) was added so as to make the final volume 5.0 ml. As the complex was insoluble in water, 20 ml. of ethyl alcohol was added so that the final volume in all the cases was 25.0 ml. The proportion of alcohol in solution will be 80%. The systems studied are presented graphically in fig. 3.

FIG. 2(a)

FIG 2(b)

4. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113; *ibid.*, 1936, **6**, 97; *vide* Martell and Calvin, *Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds*, 1st edition, 1956, Prentice Hall Inc., N. J. p. 29.

DISCUSSION

The ratio of the slopes (Fig. 2) indicate that the formula of the complexes are $\text{Ni}(\text{DDTC})_2$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{DDTC})_3$. The Job's method (Fig. 3.) indicates that the formula of the complexes are $\text{Cu}(\text{DDTC})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{DDTC})_2$, and $\text{UO}_2(\text{DDTC})_3$.

FIG. 3

- (A) $\text{UO}_2(\text{Ac})_2$ 0.001M + NaDDTC 0.001M : Water
 (B) $\text{UO}_2(\text{Ac})_2$ 0.0005M + NaDDTC 0.0005M : Water
 (C) CuSO_4 0.001M + NaDDTC 0.001M : 80% $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$
 (D) CuSO_4 0.0005M + NaDDTC 0.0005M : 80% $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$
 (E) $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ 0.005M + NaDDTC 0.05M : 75% dioxan
 (F) $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ 0.0025M + NaDDTC 0.0025M : 75% dioxan.

FIG. 3(a)

FIG. 3(b)

FIG. 3 (c)

Unfortunately, attempts to calculate the stability constants by any of the procedures^{5,6} based on spectrophotometric method did not yield concordant results.

5. Anderson, et. al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1195; *ibid.*, 1949, **71**, 909-912.

6. Dey, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **25**, 1260.

Reasons for this are not clearly understood. Alternative attempts were made to calculate stability constants by potentiometric methods but they were unsuccessful because of the high stability constants, the low solubility of the chelate in water and the decomposition of the free ligand at low pH .

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